

1 **Control of Xist by Rif1 demonstrates a role for double-strand break DNA repair in Xist activation.**

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6 We recently demonstrated control of the non-coding RNA that functions in dosage compensation in
7 humans, Xist, by the two major cellular tumor suppressors, p53 and Rb1, demonstrated that activation of Xist
8 occurs in females with breast cancer and in males with lung cancer, finding that aberrant Xist modulation
9 occurs in human solid tissue transformation (cancer) and demonstrating a mechanism that accounts for Xist
10 activation in transformation. We next discovered control of Xist both by the p53-associated molecule 53bp1, as
11 well as a major breast cancer susceptibility gene, BRCA1. 53bp1 and BRCA1 have functions in DNA damage
12 repair. 53bp1 is associated with double-strand break resection in conjunction with a second nuclear effector,
13 Rif1. We demonstrate here control of Xist activation by Rif1.

